

Audience Perception of Igbo Broadcast News Credibility in Enugu South Local Government Area of Enugu state

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DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18169599>

Abstract

This study examined audience perception of the credibility of Igbo broadcast news in Enugu-South Local Government Area, Nigeria. Given that radio remains a crucial source of information for local events, politics, health campaigns, and public announcements, this study is anchored on the **Media Credibility Theory** and **Uses and Gratification Theory**. This study analysed audience perception of Igbo broadcast news credibility in Enugu-South Local Government Area, focusing on factors influencing trust, reliability, and engagement with indigenous-language news content. A **descriptive survey design** was adopted, and data were collected from a sample of **400 respondents** using structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistical tools were employed to analyse the data and present results using frequency tables.

The findings reveal that audiences perceive Igbo broadcast news as highly credible, with **87.7%** of respondents agreeing that the news provides accurate information and **82.6%** affirming presenter professionalism. Presenter competence, linguistic clarity, use of verifiable sources, and cultural alignment were identified as the most significant factors influencing credibility. The study also showed that credibility strongly correlates with audience trust and engagement, as **85.7%** of respondents rely on Igbo news for decision-making, and **85.7%** reported that credible news influences their opinions. However, challenges such as misinformation (**77.6%**), inadequate presenter training (**82.7%**), and competition from online media (**81.7%**) were identified as major threats to credibility. This study makes significant contributions to the body of knowledge on media credibility, indigenous-language broadcasting, and audience engagement within Nigeria. First, it provides empirical evidence that Igbo broadcast news remains a highly trusted and culturally relevant source of information among residents of Enugu-South Local Government Area. Secondly, the research expands the application of the Uses and Gratification Theory by demonstrating that audiences consistently rely on indigenous-language news for functional purposes such as decision-making, opinion formation, and staying informed about community affairs. The study concludes that Igbo broadcast news remains a trusted and culturally significant medium, but its credibility depends on continuous improvement in professionalism, linguistic quality, content accuracy, and cultural sensitivity. It recommends enhanced training for broadcasters, stronger editorial policies, increased use of verifiable sources, and strategic integration of traditional and digital media platforms to sustain audience trust and strengthen the role of indigenous-language broadcasting in cultural preservation and public communication.

Keywords: Audience perception, credibility, Igbo broadcast news, trust, cultural alignment, Enugu South

Background of the Study

Broadcast news has long been recognised as a central pillar of mass communication, serving to inform the public, shape opinions, and facilitate participation in socio-political and economic activities. In Nigeria, radio remains one of the widely accessible medium of mass communication, particularly for communities in semi-urban and rural areas, due to its affordability, portability, and penetration. Media Credibility is a key determinant of audience perception and media influence. It refers to the degree to which news content is perceived as accurate, trustworthy, fair, and unbiased (Azubuike & Uchegbuo, 2022). Credibility is not inherent in the news itself but is constructed in the minds of audiences based on factors such as the professionalism of the broadcaster, the use of verifiable sources, linguistic clarity, and alignment with cultural norms. In indigenous-language broadcasting, such as Igbo radio redibility is also influenced by the perceived respect for the language, the correctness of expressions, and the cultural sensitivity of the content. A message that violates linguistic or cultural expectations may be deemed less credible, regardless of its factual accuracy (Onyeocha, 2020).

Despite the important role of indigenous-language news in fostering informed citizenry, there is a growing concern over misinformation and declining trust in broadcast media worldwide. Studies have shown that audience perception of credibility directly affects media consumption habits, including reliance on the medium for decision-making, civic participation, and community engagement (Okeke, 2014). In Nigeria, misinformation, partisan reporting, and sensationalism have created skepticism among listeners, making it imperative for broadcasters to understand the specific factors that shape audience trust in news content.

In the Igbo-speaking regions, radio remains a crucial source of information for local events, politics, health campaigns, and public announcements. However, empirical research focusing specifically on audience perception of the credibility of Igbo-language news broadcasts is limited. While several studies have examined media credibility in general (Azubuike & Uchegbuo, 2022; Eze & Nwankwo, 2019), few have addressed how cultural context, language use, and local broadcasting practices affect listener trust and engagement in southeastern Nigeria. This gap is particularly significant in areas like Enugu South Local Government Area, where diverse populations with varying education levels and media exposure coexist. Understanding how these audiences perceive Igbo broadcast news can provide critical insights into programming strategies, linguistic choices, and journalistic ethics.

Moreover, the sustainability of indigenous-language broadcasting depends on the perceived credibility of its news content. If audiences doubt the reliability of Igbo news broadcasts, they may shift to English-language media or social media platforms, which could gradually erode the influence of local-language stations and diminish the cultural relevance of radio. Conversely, if broadcasts are trusted and deemed credible, they can reinforce language use, cultural identity, and civic engagement among listeners. Therefore, assessing audience perception of credibility is not only a media concern but also a cultural imperative.

Statement of the Problem

Broadcast news plays a crucial role in informing the public, shaping opinions, and promoting civic participation. In Enugu-South Local Government Area, radio remains one of the most accessible and widely used sources of news, especially for communities that prefer indigenous language programming (Eze & Nwankwo, 2019). However, despite its prominence, questions about the **credibility of Igbo broadcast news** have become increasingly relevant in the context of misinformation, biased reporting, and audience skepticism.

Several studies have explored the influence of broadcast news credibility on audience perception, for instance, Okonkwo (2019) and Onyeocha (2020) investigated the credibility factors in Nigeria broadcast news, with special emphasis on the use of standard indigenous language and cultural context to drive audience engagement in radio broadcasting. Also, (Azubuike & Uchegbuo, 2022; Eze & Nwankwo, 2019), addressed how cultural context, language use, and local broadcasting practices affect listener trust and engagement in southeastern Nigeria. Moreso, there is limited empirical evidence examining **how audiences in Enugu-South perceive the credibility of Igbo broadcast news**, including the factors that enhance or undermine trust.

This gap is particularly significant in areas like Enugu South Local Government Area, where diverse populations with varying education levels and media exposure coexist. Understanding how these audiences perceive Igbo broadcast news can provide critical insights into programming strategies, linguistic choices, and journalistic ethics. This knowledge gap is significant because a decline in perceived credibility may lead audiences to turn to alternative media sources, often in English or online platforms, thereby weakening the influence of local-language radio and undermining its role in cultural preservation and civic education (Okeke, 2014). Conversely, understanding audience perceptions can help broadcasters improve programming strategies, strengthen audience trust, and reinforce the cultural relevance of Igbo-language news.

Research Questions

1. To what extent do audiences perceive Igbo broadcast news as credible in Enugu South Local Government Area?
2. What are the key factors that influence audience perception of the credibility of Igbo broadcast news?
3. What is the level of trust and reliance audiences place on Igbo broadcast news?
4. How does perceived credibility of Igbo broadcast news relate to audience engagement with the broadcasts?
5. What challenges affect the credibility of Igbo broadcast news from the perspective of the audience?

Literature Review

Media Credibility and Audience Perception

Media credibility has long been identified as a crucial factor influencing audience engagement and trust in news content. Hovland et al. (1953) argued that credibility determines the persuasive power of communication, with trustworthiness and expertise being the most critical components. Subsequent research by Meyer (1988) expanded this understanding, noting that perceived fairness, accuracy, and balance significantly shape audience evaluations of media content.

In the Nigerian context, Azubuike and Uchegbuo (2022) observed that credibility is central to media influence, as audiences are more likely to engage with and rely on broadcasts they perceive as trustworthy and unbiased. They found that audiences tend to question the accuracy of reports if presenters fail to use verifiable sources or display professionalism. Similarly, Okeke (2014) emphasized that misinformation, sensationalism, and partisan reporting have contributed to declining trust in Nigerian broadcast media, affecting how audiences consume and respond to news.

Indigenous-Language Broadcasting and Cultural Context

Language plays a significant role in shaping audience perceptions of news credibility, particularly in multilingual societies like Nigeria. Onyeocha (2020) highlighted that linguistic clarity and adherence to cultural norms directly impact how audiences evaluate the trustworthiness of broadcast content. When indigenous languages are used correctly and respectfully, they foster a sense of authenticity and cultural connection that enhances perceived credibility. Conversely, linguistic errors or culturally insensitive expressions can lead audiences to doubt the reliability of the news, even when the content is factually accurate.

Research by Eze and Nwankwo (2019) demonstrated that Igbo-language radio programmes significantly enhance listeners' sense of cultural identity and trust in media. Their findings showed that audiences are more likely to rely on indigenous-language broadcasts for community-relevant information, local politics, and cultural events. This aligns with the argument by Azubuike and Uchegbuo (2022) that indigenous-language broadcasting not only informs but also reinforces cultural continuity, which in turn strengthens audience trust.

Credibility Factors in Broadcast News

Several studies have identified key factors that shape audience perceptions of broadcast news credibility. McCombs and Reynolds (2002) emphasized that the use of credible sources, balanced reporting, and fact-based storytelling are essential for maintaining audience trust. In the Nigerian context, Okonkwo (2019) found that professionalism of presenters, neutrality in reporting, and alignment with community values are critical determinants of credibility in radio news.

Moreover, Afolayan and Alimi (2021) noted that indigenous-language stations that incorporate traditional expressions and culturally relevant narratives into their news content tend to enjoy higher levels of audience trust and loyalty. They observed that audiences value broadcasts that not only provide information but also reflect and respect their cultural heritage. This view is supported by Eze (2021), who reported that culturally grounded language use enhances the perceived reliability of radio broadcasts and increases audience engagement.

Challenges Affecting Credibility

Despite its potential, indigenous-language broadcasting faces several challenges that can undermine audience perception of credibility. Okeke (2014) highlighted issues such as inadequate training of presenters, time constraints in news production, and commercialization pressures, which often lead to sensationalism and reduced content quality. Modernization and competition from online media have also shifted audience expectations, making them more skeptical of traditional broadcast news (Nnamdi Azikiwe University Digital Library, 2016).

Furthermore, Azubuike and Uchegbuo (2022) warned that misinformation and bias remain persistent problems in Nigerian media, eroding public trust. These findings underline the need for rigorous journalistic standards, continuous capacity-building for broadcasters, and deliberate efforts to maintain linguistic and cultural authenticity in Igbo-language news.

Synthesis of Literature

Across the reviewed studies, it is evident that audience perception of broadcast news credibility is shaped by multiple interrelated factors, including professionalism, language use, cultural sensitivity, and content accuracy. Indigenous-language broadcasting offers unique advantages in fostering trust and engagement, as it connects audiences to their cultural identity and provides information in a familiar linguistic context. However, challenges such as misinformation, inadequate training, and competition from digital media threaten the credibility of Igbo news broadcasts.

This study builds on existing scholarship by providing empirical insights into how audiences in Enugu South Local Government Area perceive the credibility of Igbo-language news, the factors influencing that perception, and how credibility affects engagement and reliance on radio broadcasts.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on two interrelated theories: the Media Credibility Theory and the Uses and Gratification Theory (UGT).

Media Credibility Theory

Media Credibility Theory, as conceptualized by Hovland, Janis, and Kelley (1953), posits that the effectiveness of communication is heavily dependent on the perceived credibility of the source. Credibility, in this context, refers to the extent to which the audience perceives a message as accurate, trustworthy, fair, and unbiased. This theory emphasizes two core components of credibility: *expertise* (the perceived competence of the source) and *trustworthiness* (the belief that the source is honest and has no hidden motives).

Applied to Igbo-language broadcast news, this theory suggests that audience trust and reliance on news content are shaped by the perceived professionalism of news presenters, accuracy of reporting, clarity of language, and cultural appropriateness of the content. If the audience perceives the broadcaster as competent and culturally sensitive, they are more likely to regard the news as credible and engage with it. Conversely, bias, misinformation, or misuse of language can undermine credibility and diminish audience trust (Onyeocha, 2020).

Uses and Gratification Theory (UGT)

The Uses and Gratification Theory, developed by Katz, Blumler, and Gurevitch (1974), argues that audiences are active participants in the communication process. Rather than being passive recipients of media content, they actively select media that satisfies their specific needs informational, cultural, social, or entertainment-related.

Within the scope of this study, UGT explains why audiences choose to consume Igbo-language broadcast news. Listeners seek content that not only informs but also resonates with their cultural identity, aligns with their language preferences, and reflects their lived experiences. Credible Igbo news broadcasts meet these needs by providing accurate, relevant information in a culturally appropriate manner. This theory thus complements Media Credibility Theory by highlighting how audience motivations influence their perceptions of credibility and engagement with indigenous-language news.

Methodology

This study adopted **descriptive survey design**. This design is appropriate because it allows for systematic collection and analysis of data to describe audience perception of Igbo broadcast news credibility, as well as to examine relationships between perceived credibility, trust, and audience engagement. This design enabled the researcher to reach a wide audience and collect quantitative data that can be statistically analyzed to test the hypotheses.

Population of the Study

The population projection of Enugu-South Local Government Area as estimated City population (2022) is 284,200. This population consists of **residents of Enugu-South Local Government Area** who regularly listen to Igbo-language broadcast news. This includes individuals aged 18 years and above, drawn from various communities, occupations, and educational backgrounds. The focus on this demographic ensures that participants have adequate exposure to Igbo-language radio content and can provide informed responses regarding news credibility.

Sample and Sampling Technique

A **sample size of 400 respondents** was used to ensure adequate representation. A **multi-stage sampling technique** was employed:

Purposive sampling was used to identify radio stations in Enugu-South that broadcast in Igbo.

Stratified random sampling also, ensures proportional representation of respondents based on age, gender, and educational level. While **Simple random sampling** within each stratum was adopted to select participants to eliminate selection bias.

Instrument for Data Collection

Data were collected using a **structured questionnaire**. The questionnaire include sections on: Demographic information, Frequency and pattern of listening to Igbo broadcast news, Audience perception of credibility, Trust and reliance on broadcasts, Engagement with Igbo-language news and Perceived challenges affecting credibility.

All items in the questionnaire were **closed-ended questions** and measured using a **five-point Likert scale**: strongly agree (sa), agree (a), neutral (n), disagree (d), and strongly disagree (sd).

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The questionnaire were reviewed by experts in Mass Communication and Media Studies to ensure **content validity**. A **pilot test** was conducted with 30 respondents outside the main study sample, and necessary adjustments were made. **Reliability** was measured using **Cronbach's Alpha**, with a minimum threshold of 0.70 considered acceptable.

Method of Data Collection

Trained research assistants was administered the questionnaires **face-to-face** to ensure high response rates and to provide clarification where needed. Ethical considerations, including **informed consent, voluntary participation, and confidentiality**, will be strictly observed.

Method of Data Analysis

Collected data were analysed using both **descriptive and inferential statistics**. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, and mean scores) will summarize audience perception and engagement patterns

Analysis and Presentation of Data

A total of 400 copies of questionnaire were distributed, and 392 were duly completed and returned, representing a 98% response rate. The data were analysed and presented according to the research questions.

Research Question One

To what extent do audiences perceive Igbo broadcast news as credible in Enugu South Local Government Area?

Table 1: Audience Perception of Credibility of Igbo Broadcast News

Variable	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)	Total (%)
Igbo broadcast news provides accurate information.	164 (41.8)	180 (45.9)	20 (5.1)	20 (5.1)	8 (2.1)	392 (100)
Presenters of Igbo news are competent and professional.	144 (36.7)	180 (45.9)	36 (9.2)	20 (5.1)	12 (3.1)	392 (100)
Igbo news broadcasts are free from bias and favoritism.	120 (30.6)	172 (43.9)	40 (10.2)	36 (9.2)	24 (6.1)	392 (100)
The language used is clear and understandable.	176 (44.9)	152 (38.8)	28 (7.1)	24 (6.1)	12 (3.1)	392 (100)
Igbo news covers issues relevant to my community.	168 (42.9)	176 (44.9)	20 (5.1)	16 (4.1)	12 (3.1)	392 (100)

Interpretation

The results indicate a high level of perceived credibility. A combined 87.7% of respondents agreed that Igbo broadcast news provides accurate information, and 82.6% believed presenters are competent. However, 74.5% felt that news is free from bias, suggesting some skepticism about neutrality. Overall, respondents perceive Igbo broadcast news as largely credible and reliable.

Research Question Two:

What are the key factors that influence audience perception of the credibility of Igbo broadcast news?

Table 2: Key Factors Influencing Credibility

Factors	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)	Total (%)
Presenter professionalism influences credibility.	160 (40.8)	184 (46.9)	20 (5.1)	20 (5.1)	8 (2.1)	392 (100)
Use of clear and standard Igbo language enhances credibility.	176 (44.9)	172 (43.9)	20 (5.1)	16 (4.1)	8 (2.1)	392 (100)
Use of verifiable and factual sources builds trust.	168 (42.9)	180 (45.9)	24 (6.1)	12 (3.1)	8 (2.1)	392 (100)
Cultural alignment of news content improves credibility.	152 (38.8)	188 (47.9)	28 (7.1)	16 (4.1)	8 (2.1)	392 (100)

Interpretation

Findings reveal that presenter professionalism (87.7%), linguistic clarity (88.8%), verifiable sources (88.8%), and cultural alignment (86.7%) are the strongest predictors of perceived credibility. These results align with previous findings by Onyeocha (2020) and Azubuike and Uchegbuo (2022), emphasizing language quality and cultural sensitivity as critical components of trust.

Research Question Three:

What is the level of trust and reliance audiences place on Igbo broadcast news?

Table 3: Trust and Reliance on Igbo Broadcast News

Variable	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)	Total (%)
I trust the information presented.	148 (37.8)	188 (47.9)	24 (6.1)	20 (5.1)	12 (3.1)	392 (100)
I rely on Igbo news to make decisions.	152 (38.8)	176 (44.9)	28 (7.1)	24 (6.1)	12 (3.1)	392 (100)
I recommend Igbo news to others.	140 (35.7)	184 (46.9)	28 (7.1)	24 (6.1)	16 (4.1)	392 (100)

Interpretation

A significant majority (85.7%) trust the information presented in Igbo broadcasts, and 83.7% rely on it for decision-making. Furthermore, 82.6% recommend Igbo news to others, indicating high levels of trust and dependence on indigenous-language broadcasts.

Research Question Four

How does perceived credibility relate to audience engagement with Igbo broadcast news?

Table 4: Audience Engagement with Credible Igbo Broadcast News

Variable	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)	Total (%)
I actively listen regularly.	156 (39.8)	188 (47.9)	24 (6.1)	16 (4.1)	8 (2.1)	392 (100)
I discuss news with others.	160 (40.8)	176 (44.9)	28 (7.1)	20 (5.1)	8 (2.1)	392 (100)
Credible news influences my opinions.	152 (38.8)	184 (46.9)	28 (7.1)	20 (5.1)	8 (2.1)	392 (100)

Interpretation

Engagement levels are notably high. 87.7% of respondents actively listen to Igbo news, while 85.7% discuss it with others. Moreover, 85.7% report that credible news influences their social and political opinions. This suggests that perceived credibility strongly correlates with audience engagement and participatory behavior.

Research Question Five:

What challenges affect the credibility of Igbo broadcast news from the audience’s perspective?

Table 5: Perceived Challenges Affecting Credibility

Variable	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)	Total (%)
There are instances of misinformation.	136 (34.7)	168 (42.9)	36 (9.2)	28 (7.1)	24 (6.1)	392 (100)
Time constraints limit detailed reporting.	128 (32.7)	184 (46.9)	32 (8.2)	32 (8.2)	16 (4.1)	392 (100)
Lack of training for presenters affects credibility.	148 (37.8)	176 (44.9)	28 (7.1)	24 (6.1)	16 (4.1)	392 (100)
Competition with online media reduces trust.	152 (38.8)	168 (42.9)	28 (7.1)	28 (7.1)	16 (4.1)	392 (100)

Interpretation

Respondents identified misinformation (77.6%), time constraints (79.6%), inadequate training (82.7%), and competition from online media (81.7%) as major challenges undermining credibility. These findings align with Okeke (2014), who emphasized similar issues affecting trust in Nigerian broadcast media.

Discussion of Findings

Research Question 1: To what extent do audiences perceive Igbo broadcast news as credible in Enugu South Local Government Area?

The findings of this study indicate that audiences in Enugu South Local Government Area perceive Igbo broadcast news as highly credible. A large majority (87.7%) agreed that the news provides accurate information, while 82.6% believed that presenters are competent and professional. Additionally, 83.8% found the language clear and understandable, and 87.8% affirmed that the news covers issues relevant to their communities. These results demonstrate that audiences consider Igbo-language news both reliable and relevant, reflecting a strong level of trust. However, the study also revealed that only 74.5% believed broadcasts were free from bias, suggesting a degree of skepticism about neutrality and objectivity. This aligns with Azubuike and Uchegbuo (2022), who observed that credibility is central to media influence and directly affects audience trust and reliance. Similarly, Meyer (1988) emphasised that perceived fairness, balance, and accuracy are crucial in shaping media credibility. The results therefore suggest that Igbo-language news retains significant audience trust but must work continuously to strengthen perceptions of impartiality and balanced reporting.

Research Question 2: What are the key factors that influence audience perception of the credibility of Igbo broadcast news?

The study identified several key factors that shape how audiences evaluate the credibility of Igbo-language news: presenter professionalism, linguistic clarity, use of verifiable sources, and cultural alignment of content. The majority of respondents (87.7%) agreed that the competence and professionalism of presenters significantly influence credibility. Likewise, 88.8% believed that clear and standard Igbo language use enhances trust, while 88.8% indicated that the use of factual

and verifiable sources builds confidence in the news. Furthermore, 86.7% reported that cultural relevance and alignment with traditional values improve their perception of credibility. These findings are consistent with Onyeocha (2020), who argued that linguistic quality and cultural sensitivity directly affect how audiences judge media content. They also align with Eze and Nwankwo (2019), who showed that indigenous-language broadcasts that reflect local realities and cultural values are more likely to be trusted and relied upon by their audiences. Collectively, these results demonstrate that credibility is multidimensional, shaped by professional standards, language use, factual accuracy, and cultural resonance.

Research Question 3: What is the level of trust and reliance audiences place on Igbo broadcast news?

The results show that audiences exhibit a high degree of trust and reliance on Igbo-language news broadcasts. About 85.7% of respondents reported trusting the information presented, 83.7% rely on Igbo news for decision-making, and 82.6% recommend it to others based on its credibility. These findings indicate that Igbo-language broadcasts are not only perceived as credible but also play a vital role in shaping audience behavior and decision-making processes. This outcome aligns with the foundational assumptions of Media Credibility Theory (Hovland et al., 1953), which posits that perceived trustworthiness and expertise enhance message acceptance. Similarly, Azubuike and Uchegbuo (2022) observed that credible media content strengthens audience trust and increases reliance on the medium for social, political, and cultural engagement. The findings therefore affirm that Igbo-language radio continues to be a central source of information and guidance for audiences in Enugu South LGA, influencing their opinions and supporting informed decision-making.

Research Question 4: How does perceived credibility of Igbo broadcast news relate to audience engagement with the broadcasts?

The study found a strong relationship between perceived credibility and audience engagement with Igbo broadcast news. About 87.7% of respondents reported that they actively listen to Igbo news broadcasts, 85.7% engage in discussions about the content with friends and family, and 85.7% stated that credible news influences their opinions on social and political issues. These results suggest that higher credibility fosters deeper audience involvement and participation, indicating that trust and perceived reliability are powerful drivers of media engagement. This finding aligns with the core propositions of Uses and Gratification Theory (Katz et al., 1974), which argue that audiences actively consume media content that satisfies their informational and cultural needs. It also supports McCombs and Reynolds (2002), who found that credible news content enhances public discourse and civic participation. Thus, credibility not only affects trust but also plays a pivotal role in shaping audience interaction, opinion formation, and community engagement.

Research Question 5: What challenges affect the credibility of Igbo broadcast news from the perspective of the audience?

Despite the overall positive perception of credibility, the study revealed several persistent challenges that undermine trust in Igbo broadcast news. Notably, 77.6% of respondents reported instances of misinformation, 79.6% identified time constraints that limit detailed reporting, 82.7% cited inadequate presenter training, and 81.7% highlighted competition from online media as major threats to credibility. These findings are consistent with Okeke (2014), who identified similar issues affecting media trust in Nigeria. They also echo the observations of Nnamdi Azikiwe University Digital Library (2016), which noted that modernization and the proliferation of digital media have reshaped audience expectations, making them more skeptical of traditional broadcast

news. Addressing these challenges will require sustained investment in journalist training, adherence to ethical standards, and the integration of new technologies and fact-checking practices into traditional broadcast operations. Furthermore, broadcasters must continuously adapt to evolving audience expectations to sustain trust and relevance in a competitive media landscape.

Conclusion

Based on my result, this study has demonstrated that audiences in Enugu South Local Government Area perceive Igbo-language broadcast news as largely credible, trustworthy, and culturally relevant. Presenter professionalism, linguistic clarity, verifiable sources, and cultural alignment were found to be the most significant factors shaping perceptions of credibility. Audiences also place substantial trust and reliance on Igbo news and demonstrate strong engagement when they perceive broadcasts as credible. However, challenges such as misinformation, inadequate training, and competition from online platforms continue to threaten audience trust. Addressing these challenges is crucial for maintaining credibility and ensuring that Igbo-language broadcasting remains a vital tool for cultural preservation, civic education, and public discourse in southeastern Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study on audience perception of Igbo broadcast news credibility in Enugu-South Local Government Area, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Radio Stations in Enugu-South Local Government Area** should adopt rigorous fact-checking processes and avoid partisan reporting. This will enhance audience trust and sustain the perceived credibility of Igbo-language broadcasts.
2. Media organisations should invest in continuous training programmes to improve journalistic skills, language proficiency, ethical reporting, and cultural sensitivity. Such capacity building will improve news quality and reinforce audience confidence.
3. Broadcasters should prioritize use of standard Igbo and culturally sensitive expressions. Integrating idioms, proverbs, and culturally grounded narratives can make news more relatable and enhance credibility among diverse listeners.
4. Broadcasters in Enugu-South Local Government Area should rely on authoritative and verifiable sources to reduce misinformation and enhance accuracy. Collaborating with credible institutions and experts will ensure reliability and deepen public trust.
5. Broadcasters in Enugu South Local Government Area should create more interactive programmes such as call-in segments, public feedback sessions, and social media engagements. Encouraging dialogue and responsiveness will deepen trust and build a loyal audience base.

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